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EPICROCIS NEFTAELLA (LUCAS, 1911), NEW SPECIES
FOR THE MALTESE ISLANDS (*Lepidoptera Pyralidae Phycitinae*)

SUMMARY

Epicrocis neftaella (Lucas, 1911) is here recorded for the first time from the Maltese Islands. Distribution of the species and larval foodplant is noted.

Key words. New record, distribution.

RIASSUNTO

Epicrocis neftaella (Lucas, 1911) è qui segnalata per la prima volta dalle isole maltesi. Sono riportate inoltre la distribuzione della specie e le piante nutrici delle larve.

Parole chiave. Prima segnalazione, distribuzione.

INTRODUCTION

Epicrocis neftaella, originally described by LUCAS (1911: 218) in the genus *Salebria* Zeller, and later transferred to *Epicrocis* Zeller, by FALCK *et al.* (2019: 33), was described from a female specimen collected in March of 1914 from Nefta in Tunisia.

This species has to date been recorded from North Africa, from Tunisia (LUCAS, 1911), Morocco, Libya, and Algeria (LERAUT, 2021). In Europe it has been recorded from the Canary Islands (FALCK *et al.*, 2019). From the literature, throughout its range, the species appears to be very rare as only single

specimens are mentioned. The larvae have been recorded feeding on *Acacia tortilis* (Forssk.) Hayne (LERAUT, 2014: 344). *Prunus amygdalus* Batsch, 1801 (MEYRICK, 1934: 492) is a foodplant of a different species *Epicrocis anthracanthes* Meyrick, 1934, which was incorrectly synonymized with *E. nefstaella* by LERAUT (2014); see SLAMKA (2019) and currently it is a synonym of *Kreadere argyrophanes* (Meyrick, 1937) known in Europe from Cyprus only.

Fig. 1 — *Epicrocis nefstaella* (Lucas, 1911) collected in Malta at light in 2023.

MATERIAL EXAMINED – MALTA, (♂) Rabat, [35.876N; 14.395E., 200m.], 3.x.2023 [taken at light]. P. Sammut leg.

CONCLUSION

The night between October 22nd and 23rd, the Maltese Islands experienced a SE wind with a speed of between 2 and 20km per hour. The moon was in its first quarter. The average temperature was about 23°C and the night was slightly cloudy with humidity of about 89%. The moth trap, with 2 UV, 8W tubes was lit up from 20.00 hours on the 22nd to about 06.00 hours of the 23rd. No less than 33 different species, for a total of 107 specimens, mostly from the Noctuidae were recorded and a good number of these are conside-

red migratory species. Because of the prevailing weather conditions, the strength and direction of the wind on the night the specimen was recorded, it is not impossible that *Epicrocis neftaella* reached Malta by wind assisted migration from North Africa. For this species, we propose the vernacular name Bahrija għiza ta' Nefta.

REFERENCES

- FALCK P., KARSHOLT O. & SLAMKA F., 2019. New data o Pyraloidea from the Canary Islands, Spain (Lepidoptera: Pyraloidea). *SHILAP, Rev. lepidopter.*, 47(185): 33-48.
- LERAUT G., 2021. A Phycitinae species new to the Algerian Sahara (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). *Rev. fr. Entom gén.*, 3(4): 88-92.
- LERAUT P., 2014. Pyralids 2 – Moths of Europe. Vol.4. *N.A.P. edition*, Verrieres le Buisson, 440pp.
- LUCAS D., 1911. Lepidopteres nouveaux de Tunisie. *Bull. Soc. entom. France*, 1911: 217-219.
- MEYRICK E., 1934. Exotic Microlepidoptera. *Taylor & Francis*, London, 4(16): 481-512.
- SLAMKA F., 2019. Phycitinae. – Pyraloidea of Europe 4(1), *Slamka Publ.*, Bratislava, 432pp.

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